

A STUDY ON STUDENTS BEHAVIOR TOWARDS ONLINE LEARNING DURING COVID-19 PANDEMIC

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Abstract:

The break-down of the Covid-19 pandemic has changed the situation of the educational sector from traditional i.e.; face-to-face learning to online learning. The present study aims to know the behaviour of students towards online learning and the problem faced by them. The research is descriptive. The data is been collected through an online survey method from 76 undergraduate students. A convenient sampling is been used to collect the data. The data is been collected with the help of a questionnaire and interview. The data is been analysed using MS-Excel. It was revealed that 77.6% of students consider online learning an effective and better choice of learning. Moreover, students feel that online learning is better than going to college. This study has also given insight into the problems or barriers faced by students during online learning. The major problem faced by students while online learning is internet connectivity is poorly followed by eye strain, increase stress, and homework. A suggestive measure was recommended for the improvement of the problem faced by the student. The laziness of students is more in online learning. Hopefully, the results of this study will help in improving students' behaviour towards online learning during the Covid-19 pandemic. Furthermore, dimensions can be studied on this topic.

Key Words: *Online Learning, Student Behaviour, Pandemic*

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Introduction

The first case of Corona Virus a deadly disease found in Wuhan, China in December 2019 which spread in various parts of countries very rapidly. On 11th March, World Health Organization (WHO) declared it as a pandemic. This shutdown was done for the prevention

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of the inhibited spread of the coronavirus and for maintaining social distance. This outbreak has affected India very rapidly. This crisis had affection the education sector devastatingly. Everything was on hold. Education is one of the most important sectors for economic growth. The worldwide lockdown has led to the closedown of schools, colleges, universities for time being. This sudden closure of all academic activities has made a huge loss in learning. As per the report of UNESCO report, from June 2020, about 1.2 billion children and youth have faced disturbance from a change in the education system whereas, 200 million students have been left out from the institutions worldwide. During this period many institutions started online modes of learning to maintain their education system. An alternative way of learning was developed for students instead of face-to-face learning. This was the only option available to carry out the smooth running of academic activities also with precautions. This sudden switch from traditional learning to online learning has impacted many students as they were not techno professionals. The use of technology has impacted students as well as a teacher for making a proper plan to be executed. As the behavior of humans differs from person to person. Some have positively taken online learning whereas some take it negatively. Online learning has changed students' minds side towards learning. A google class method has been adopted by many schools and colleges. The question arises was this online learning comfortable to all. India is a developing country where the major population comes from poor and middle-class families where there is no availability smartphone smart phone, laptop and Wi-Fi access is not possible. Sudden introduction to online learning has impacted students' behavior towards learning.

Literature Review

(Raskova, like, & Muslimin, 2020) Studied on students' perspective towards online learning along with the barriers and alternative modes used for the online classroom during the Covid-19 pandemic period. The study is based on the use of two learning management systems i.e.; Moodle and Google classroom. The data was collected through a questionnaire and interview method. It was found that students faced three barriers during online learning that is unfamiliarity, slow internet, and physical conditions which includes eye strain. The study proposed to overcome barriers by quick feedback, more interaction, connecting video material to audio, giving breaks to overcome psychical barriers.

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(Ullah, Khan, & Khan, 2017) examined the attitude of undergraduate students toward online learning. The study was carried out in the Peshawar district. The aim was to find the relationship of students with the technology acceptance model, specifically to online learning. A questionnaire was distributed to collect the data. The data were collected from 83 undergraduate students. Regression analysis was used to analyze the data. It was revealed there is an insignificant relationship was found between students' interest, usefulness, easiness in computer online learning. Slow internet facility has developed a negative impact on students for online learning. Further, the recommendation was given to the government for the introduction of e-learning to be added to the curriculum, organize workshops for teachers, and provide training to a teacher for use of computer applications.

(Mohalik & Sahool, 2020) studied on e-readiness and perception towards online learning of students and teachers. The online survey was used to collect the data. It was found positive relation with e-readiness with a digital device and financial support with teachers whereas there was lack of internet connectivity, electricity supply and personal home space for students. However, 35% of students and teachers were experienced in digital use. It was also found that the interaction of student and teacher is very less in online learning. A remarkable number of student-teachers were found stressed and had poor confidence in the online platform. The majority accepted online learning as beneficial but the not alternate to face-to-face learning. Hence, for efficient and accessible online learning support from the government, parents, institutions, and teachers is required.

(Tommy, Ying, Aditya, & Neni, 2020) examined on student learning during the Covid-19 pandemic. The data is been collected from West Java, Indonesia. The data was collected through questionnaires and interviews of students and teachers. It was found the student interest in online learning is low and ineffective. Students feel online learning is boring. The suggestion was given to teachers to adopt video learning methods due to internet connectivity being low. This would help to increase the efficiency of online learning.

The objective of the study

- To study student behavior towards online learning.
- To evaluate problems faced by the student during online learning.

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Research Methodology

The primary data is collected through questionnaires and personal interviews of undergraduate students. The secondary data is collected from published journals, textbooks, and websites. The data is collected from 76 respondents perusing the undergraduate course. The respondent collected uses an online platform for the study during the pandemic period. The data was collected using google form and analyzed with the help of MS Excel. A pivot table is been used to draw a conclusion from the collected data.

Data Interpretation

The study aims to know student behavior towards online learning and problem faced during online learning.

Respondent Profile

The data is collected from 76 respondents based on their gender and standard. Respondents were actively involved in the online survey.

❖ Gender

Out of 76 respondents, 26 were male students i.e.; 34% and 50 were female students i.e.; 66%.

Row Labels	Count of Standard	Percentage
Female	50	66%
Male	26	34%
Grand Total	76	100%

❖ Online learning is effective

Out of 76 respondents, 59 students' response selected YES option both consist of male and female. Participation of female response is more compare to male. Hence, it was found that student feels online learning is effective.

Count of Standard Row Labels	Column Labels		Grand Total
	No	Yes	
Female	13	37	50
Male	4	22	26
Grand Total	17	59	76

❖ Behavior of Student towards online learning

The data collected shows that students prefer going college and online learning both are

effective followed by laziness during online learning. However, some students agreed on going college is better than online learning.

Behavior of student towards online learning.

❖ Problem faced during Online Learning

The data collected shows there are some common problems faced by students during online learning is internet connectivity issue, physical eye strain problem, understanding issue during online learning and tiredness.

Problem Faced while online learning

Conclusion

The Covid-19 pandemic has affected all the sectors along with education sectors. During this period, the education sector has started with online learning i.e.; learning from home. One of the methods of learning adopted all over the globe. India too accepted this modern method of learning. Based on the questionnaire and interview results, it was found most of the students feel online learning is effective. The behavior of student was studied, it was found that student

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feels whether it be online learning or offline both are effective. Even they agreed on online learning makes them lazy as there are not having any physical activities anymore. Some students complain about the poor internet connectivity during online learning. Students feel eye strain with excessive use of laptops and mobile phone for online learning Whereas, some even faced tiredness. The study is limited to student online learning. Further study can be conducted based on teacher perspective and increasing the size of the population.

Suggestion

During online learning, there should be a break for students of 15minutes. Along with that teacher must take interactive activity among students and take initiative to make online learning more effective to attract students. Government must take steps for improvement in internet connectivity

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